

Process Improvement in PT. Docil Berkah Abadi Using Business Process Improvement (BPI) Framework

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ABSTRACT: PT. Docil Berkah Abadi is a retailer that offers motorcycle accessories, primarily windshields, via e-commerce, resellers, distributors, and an offline store. Additionally, subsidiary companies sell additional varieties of accessories. Mission of this organization is to dominate the market for motorcycle accessories in Indonesia and to innovate our products via subsidiary companies. PT. Docil Berkah Abadi has serious problems in its business process because the previously running business processes are not effective and result in too large fixed costs incurred by PT. Docil berkah Abadi This is the time from the beginning of the order acceptance until the goods are sold too long. The number of employees who have been discharged does not correspond to the salary costs already incurred by PT. Docil Berkah Abadi This is a very expensive rental because you have to store a lot of stock.

The aim of this study is to improve business processes by understanding the roots of the problem with Root Cause Analysis (RCA) and improve the business process with Business Process Improvement. (BPI). The author uses five whys on Root Cause Analysis (RCA) analysis and performs identification on business early processes, and improves business by streamlining with Bureaucracy Elimination and Upgrading.

This study was conducted using qualitative methods. The researchers conducted in-depth interviews with several divisions of the company to gain insight into the business processes of the enterprise. The results of the interview showed that the business processes used by the company are still less accurate. Using interview insights, the researchers built a new process business using flowchart.

KEYWORDS: Business Process, Business Process Improvement (BPI), Root Cause Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Generally, a company's objective is to implement a successful business process. Business processes are a series of coordinated activities executed within an organizational and technical environment. This project has commercial objectives in mind (Mathias Weske, 2012). Good and accurate business processes improve the effectiveness and efficiency of an organization's or business's operations. And to have a more effective and efficient business process, it is necessary to have business process analysis and modelling that seeks to evaluate the already implemented business processes and improve the already implemented business process.

In recent years, technological advancement has been so rapid that it has made it simpler for people to do everything (Putri et al., n.d.). In modern times, the transmission of information has shifted away from print media and towards electronic media (Setiyadi & Budi Setiawan, 2017).

The expanding use of electronic media can have repercussions in numerous spheres of existence, including business. Utilising this technology can be beneficial. One aspect of PT. Docil Berkah Abadi is the digital management and integration of data and information. Business strategies and procedures are crucial to achieving the organization's objectives. A business process consists of a succession of activities carried out in coordination with the business and technical environment and with the goal of implementing a business strategy. (Mathias Weske, 2012).

The aim of PT. Docil Berkah Abadi is to manage its information systems effectively and efficiently. PT. Docil Berkah Abadi is one of the companies that uses the online system to conduct business. However, the implementation of the system from stock in to stock out still has some issues. There is a need for business process optimisation that generates business process recommendations in order to solve the issue.

I.2 Company Profile

Nature of the Firm PT. Docil Berkah Abadi is a retailer that offers motorcycle accessories, primarily windshields, via e-commerce, resellers, distributors, and an offline store. Additionally, subsidiary companies sell additional varieties of accessories. Mission of this organization is to dominate the market for motorcycle accessories in Indonesia and to innovate our products via subsidiary companies.

Offerings and Services PT. Docil Berkah Abadi is a manufacturer of motorcycle windshields and other acrylic accessories, in addition to other accessory types marketed by subsidiary companies. On-site services are available at the physical establishment. The target market consists primarily of males between the ages of 18 and 30 who ride with their community on the weekends.

Competitors of PT. Docil Berkah Abadi are other retailers selling our products or counterfeits in other Indonesian locations. The competitive advantage is best-selling windshield models from premium-class manufacturers that are sold at a discount, as well as exclusive models that are unavailable at other stores. With warranties and consumer education, provide exceptional customer service. Market share is PT. Docil Berkah Abadi dominates the motorcycle windshield market in Indonesian e-commerce with a 35 percent market share.

The Organizational Structure is hierarchical, with a distinct chain of command and each level of management being accountable for those beneath them.

I.2.1 Structure of Organization

The Organizational Structure is hierarchical, with a distinct chain of command and each level of management being accountable for those beneath them. PT. Docil Berkah Abadi has the following organizational structure:

Figure 1.1 Structure Organization PT. Docil Berkah Abadi

I.2.1 Job Description

Job description is something that is stated in writing and contains the purpose of forming a particular position or task in an organization or company. This term is also known as a job description or job description. Here is the job description in PT. Docil Berkah Abadi:

• Founder

The course has the task of managing revenue, investment, costs and also thinking about the competition between companies. Founders have an important role in planning the company’s vision and mission. In addition to, founders should also be able to decide what is good and bad for the company.

The more active the founder’s mindset is in the search for ideas, the greater the probability that founder will make the right decision.

- **Co-Founder**

Co-Founder has the task of identifying market opportunities, developing products in final form, guiding the board of directors, projecting a vision, focusing on Key Performance Indicators, making final decisions, raising funds, assessing risks, building teams, growing business, creating business documents and managing finances at PT. Docil Berkah Abadi.

- **General Director of Strategic Business Development**

Do a thorough market research. Work with teams from other divisions to meet the needs of the market. Preparing and presenting the company's business development plan. Research the company's business development on a regular basis.

- **Human Resource**

Human Resources (HR) has the task of managing the planning and development of SDM, recruitment, orientation, performance management, determination of salary, determining compensation, management of work, up to growing employment relationships between employees. HR tasks also include recruitment processes, employee salary management, training programs, preparation of employee absence reports.

- **Marketing**

Marketing is the task of creating and developing the value of a product, doing marketing or presenting products to society in various ways, producing sales or sales of products owned by the company, making product planning and establishing good relationships with consumers.

- **Finance**

The tasks and responsibilities of the finance department in a company are to manage and regulate the financial conditions of the company directly, carry out the calculation and deduction of all transaction activities or the use of company money, conduct financial transactions directly within the company or industrial plant, manage payments and bills owned by the company, such as payment of taxes, employee wages, administrative, building rental costs and the like and ensure the accuracy of data on the financial statements.

- **Packer**

A packer's primary responsibility is to collect inventories and pack them for shipment, but they can also help other warehouse tasks such as placing items in the right place back to the shelves or loading the finished package to the delivery truck.

- **Operations Manager**

As an Operation Manager, your tasks and responsibilities include directing and managing the operational team, pressuring the company's production costs, improving operational efficiency and providing full operational performance.

- **Warehouse Manager**

The Warehouse Manager's task is to manage all operational aspects of a warehouse. These tasks including trade and shipping flows, calculating and controlling stock of goods, monitoring and reporting damage, checking goods quality, carrying out order processing, overseeing staff performance financial records, and implementing warehouse operational procedural policies.

- **Warehouse (Stock In)**

The Warehouse staff is a group of workers responsible for ensuring that all products available in the warehouse are available on time and in the right quantity. They are also responsible for ensuring that the goods stored and delivered to the customer are goods of quality.

- **Warehouse (Stock Out)**

The Warehouse staff is a group of workers responsible for ensuring that all products available in the warehouse are available on time and in the right quantity. They are also responsible for ensuring that the goods stored and delivered to the customer are goods of quality. Make sure the goods come out according to the list of sold goods.

I.3 Business Issue

Good and accurate business processes improve the effectiveness and efficiency of an organization's or business's operations. And to have a more effective and efficient business process, it is necessary to have business process analysis and modelling that seeks to evaluate the already implemented business processes and improve the already implemented business process.

Improving business processes can increase the efficiency of processes that can adapt to the business and customer

requirements of PT Docil Berkah Abadi (Harrington, 1991). Enhance the business procedure. Eternal grace can aid in the growth and expansion of SME PT. Docil Berkah Abadi. Business Process Improvement can be implemented to improve business processes. Business Process Improvement is a methodical action designed to assist a company in making significant improvements to its business processes (H. James Harrington et al., 1997). Business Process Improvement begins with the mapping of the current business process. Detailed results are obtained by simulating and discussing the business process maps. The next stage is to identify the source of the issue using root cause analysis. The purpose of using root cause analysis to analysis processes is to identify deficient processes that lead to problems that negatively impact process performance. This study's Root Cause Analysis employs a 5-Why, 5-why diagram to help identify the cause factor. At the subsequent stage, enhancements can be made using tools such as streamlining, idealizing, quality factor diagram, work unit analysis, business, and benchmarking, which can be applied in accordance with the research's purpose. Streamlining is used because in streamlining there are a number of techniques that can be used to respond to the process of change, and because streamlining can simplify business processes, eliminate waste, and increase efficiency in accordance with the objectives of improvement in this research by emphasizing efficiency and effectiveness. Streamlining is the initiation of the transformation of business processes in order to establish new, improved processes that achieve the same goals. The outcomes of streamlining can reveal the level of efficacy of technology's use in business processes that can be applied to PT. Docil Berkah Abadi the results of the streamlining are then simulated based on resource and time, followed by an analysis of the disparity between the current and future business processes and the resulting impact. The expected outcomes will strengthen and enhance PT. Docil Berkah Abadi business process. Eternal Gratitude improves the efficiency of the company's business operations by generating inputs and outputs that support PT. Docil Berkah Abadi goals. PT. Docil Berkah Abadi will establish a mini-business and maximize PT. Docil Berkah Abadi growth.

PT. Docil Berkah Abadi has a serious problem in such a long and time-consuming business process, this can be shown on the table:

Table 1. 1 Early Business Process PT. Docil Berkah Abadi

Division	Early Business Process	Time (Minute)	Table Early Business Process	Time Table
AdminSeller	Export list of goods sold from all platforms	15		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Import list of sold items to Database	5		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Print Receipt and send list receipt to admin scan	15		Bureaucracy Elimination
	List of goods sold to public admin	1		Upgrading
Division	Early Business Process	Time (Minute)	Table Early Business Process	Time Table
	Excel automatically creates a list of sold items	1		Upgrading
	Receive a list of sold items from Admin Seller	1		Upgrading
	Send list of goods sold to the warehouse	1		Upgrading

AdminPublic	Export List Returns Goods from All Platforms	15	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Return of goods to warehouse.	30	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Receive list non- damaged returns to increase inventory from warehouse	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Receive list returning damaged items to increase waste from warehouse and send to finance	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Receive a list of items that are not suitable for purchase orders from the warehouse	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Coming Goods	15	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Make a Purchase Order according to inventory needs	15	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Send a Purchase Order to Finance	1	Upgrading
Division	Early Business Process	Time Table (Minute) Early Business Process	Time Table
	Acceptance of Purchase Order	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Send a Purchase Order to the Supplier	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Send a list Purchase Order to the Warehouse	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Coming Goods	15	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Receive all reports from Admin Scan	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Sending Packer Reports to Finance	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Provide proof of payment to the supplier	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Scan Sold Goods with Receipt	60	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Receive goods was packed by Team Packer	15	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Scan items and packer team	15	Bureaucracy Elimination

AdminScan	Send all reports to admin public	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Send Packer List and Items in Packing for Calculate Salary to finance	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
Finance	Receive Packer Reports to Estimate Packer Salary	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Receive list returning damaged items to increase waste	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
Division	Early Business Process	Time Table (Minute) Early Business Process	Time Table
	Receiving a Purchase Order	1	Upgrading
	Payment order to the Supplier	5	Upgrading
	Sending Proof of Payment to Public Admin	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
Packer	Receive selling goods from the warehouse	15	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Packing sold items	120	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Scan Selling goods to Admin Scan	15	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Send selling goods to the warehouse	60	Bureaucracy Elimination
Supplier	Receive Purchase Orders from Public Admin	1	Upgrading
	Receive proof of purchase order payment from admin public	1	Upgrading
	Send order to the warehouse	120	Upgrading
	Receive Adjustments of Delivered Goods and Purchase Orders from admin public	5	Upgrading
Warehouse (Stock In)	Receiving a Purchase Order from admin public	5	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Goods to Warehouse from supplier	30	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Put barcodes for all types of items	60	Bureaucracy Elimination

Division	Early Business Process	Time (Minute)	Table Early Business Process	Time Table
	Scan every barcode	15		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Barcode in Excel	1		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Goods already in barcode scan	15		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Write a letter of incoming goods and purchase order	5		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Sending letters and Qty items that are inappropriate to admin public	1		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Goods into the warehouse	30		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Goods added Inventory	1		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Receiving a return letter	1		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Sort of goods	60		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Reports of damaged items send to admin public	1		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Scan of Damaged Returned Goods	15		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Scan of returned items that are not damaged	15		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Returning damaged goods into waste	1		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Returned items not damaged enter the inventory	1		Bureaucracy Elimination
Division	Early Business Process	Time (Minute)	Table Early Business Process	Time Table
	Receive list selling goods from the admin public	1		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Prepare the sold items	60		Bureaucracy Elimination
	Scan goods for sale	15		Bureaucracy Elimination

Warehouse (Stock Out)	Delivering Goods to Packer	30	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Receive packaged items from Team Packer	5	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Scan with outgoing items. (Double Check)	30	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Return the sold goods to the warehouse	1	Bureaucracy Elimination
	Send selling goods to the expedition	1	Bureaucracy Elimination

According to the illustration on the table above PT. Docil Berkah Abadi has a long time period of 977 (Nine hundred seventy-seven) minutes in the process of stock in to stock out, this leads to the swelling of the burden of sale and fix cost that is borne by PT. Docil Berkah Abadi, otherwise the financial side cannot be optimum in compiling the existing cash flow, because of too many parties involved.

PT. Docil Berkah Abadi has serious problems in its business process because the previously running business processes are not effective and result in too large fixed costs incurred by PT. Docil berkah Abadi This is the time from the beginning of the order acceptance until the goods are sold too long. The number of employees who have been discharged does not correspond to the salary costs already incurred by PT. Docil Berkah Abadi This is a very expensive rental because you have to store a lot of stock. The amount of funds to be issued by the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi is not equal to the amount of money obtained by PT. Docil Berkah Abadi from various sales platforms. The business process through the stocking of goods is no longer effective. This causes fixed cost and variable cost that are too swollen making PT. Docil Berkah Abadi cannot optimize the existing cash flow. From some of these problems, it can be concluded that PT. Docil Berkah Abadi cannot optimize business processes and cause delayed decision-making due to ineffective cash flow as well as hindering the problems and development of PT. Docil Berkah Abadi.

I.4 Research Questions

Based on the research problem's historical context, the formulation of the problem is as follows.

1. How is the description of business processes at PT. Docil Berkah Abadi?
2. What are the problems with the business processes that have been carried out?
3. How processes and stages can be implemented to enhance PT. Docil Berkah Abadi business processes?

I.5 Research Objective

The objectives to be achieved in this research are:

1. Evaluation of business process PT. Docil Berkah Abadi.
2. Making business process more efficient PT. Docil Berkah Abadi.
3. Improvement of business processes resulting from business process analysis PT. Docil Berkah Abadi.

I.6 Research Limitation

The problem limit specified in this study is the improvement of business processes applied with a resource and time comparison.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

II.1 Theoretical Foundation

II.1.1 Business Process

Business processes are a collection of instruments used to organize an activity and improve comprehension of its interconnections (Mathias Weske, 2007). In an organization, business processes are not only established for the organization itself,

but also enable the organization to interact with the business processes of other organizations (Mathias Weske, 2012) . A business process is a collection of one or more interconnected procedures. Activities that collectively establish business or policy objectives, which typically define roles and relationships within the context of organisational structure Laguna & Marklund 2018 define "business" as an entity that distributes resources to provide the product or service the Customer desires, while "process" is a more nebulous concept with multiple meanings. It differs depending on the situation. As an instance in the universe. In biology, respiration is the "process" of life preservation. Mathematically The process of random determinism depicts the occurrence of an event. by Politics is the "clear" electoral procedure. In terms of education. It is the process of "learning" According to the 11th Edition of Merriam-Webster's Online Dictionary, (i) natural phenomenon characterised by enduring changes causes certain results, (ii) continued natural activity, or (iii) a series of actions or operations performed until completion.

Most companies spend a lot of time each year developing strategic goals and targets. Business objectives reflect the company's overall strategy. Such business goals are developed up to the departmental level, objectives are developed to measure progress in achieving specific business goals. The accumulation of activity that occurs in every business process is what ultimately determines the success of the company. With process analysis, the achievement of business goals related to customer service efficiency, effectiveness and profitability can be assured (J. Mike Jacka & Paulette J. Keller, 2009).

Mike & Keller (2009) in their book *Business Process Mapping: Improving Customer Satisfaction* 2nd Edition. Process mapping consists of several stages: process identification (studying the things that are reviewed in the process); data collection (studying what is within the process and with whom we will be involved); interview and map generation (learning and documenting actions in a process); analysis of data learning what can be done to make the process better.

II.1.2 Business Situation Analysis

Business situation analysis is a method for analyzing internal or external factors of a business to understand the business environment and its impact on business (Hitt et al., 2017). This study uses the SWOT analysis method for internal analysis and the PESTLE method for external analysis.

a) External Analysis

To mitigate threats and leverage opportunities, the firms must conduct external environment that consist of all the factors that can affect potential gain and sustain a competitive advantage (Rothaermel, 2017). One of the methods to analyze external environment is PESTEL. PESTEL framework allows the firms to scan, monitor, and evaluate the important external factors and trends that might affect upon a firm. The PESTEL model has six segments; Political, Economic, Sociocultural, Technological, Ecological, and Legal.

b) Internal Analysis

SWOT analysis is a method to find out the situation of a business by analyzing strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats whether they are profitable or not as an effort for a business to perform better (Hitt et al., 2017). Strengths and weaknesses come from the firm's internal sources so they can be controlled and can be changed. Meanwhile opportunities and threats come from external foundations so they cannot be changed but can be used to open up new opportunities and prevent the threats. The purpose of a SWOT analysis is to find out the position of a business so that it can take opportunities by avoiding or minimizing environmental threats.

II.1.3 Type of Business Process

1. Primary Process

It is a process that is related to operational so that it produces product value. There are three stages in the primary process:

1. Production
2. Marketing
3. Service to customers.

If the business has followed these three stages, it is easy for the trader to offer the product to the customer.

2. Secondary Process

In this process, what happens is not the added value but how to prepare an environment that supports the primary process. Support processes must be in line with the company's operational processes.

3. Process Management

When entering this process there is monitoring involvement to monitoring from management. Then, the management up to the management of the company's strategy should be appropriate to match the company's goals. This process also involves strategic planning to the operational management of the company.

II.1.4 Stages in the Business Process

There are several stages that are included in the business process:

1. Analysis of Activity

At this stage, both managers and employees try to plan and analysis what the company should do in a given period. This conversation becomes important to fit the needs of the company make a decision. After trying to analysis what to do in a particular period, then the next is to make and make a decision. Decision-making is related to the company's operating costs that then affect the company's activities.

2. Execution

The decision has been made and the next step is implementation. If without implementation, it would be something futile and just ending the discourse. In order for the implementation to be expected, the use of ERP software can be used to help business activities.

3. Evaluation

No business activity runs perfectly, and therefore requires evaluation not only partially but holistically. Indicators in the evaluation assessment can consist of a variety of ways. The entrepreneur can evaluate the performance of employees by their respective tasks. The objectives set by each division can be achieved. With the evaluation, the business will see where the shortcomings need to be corrected and improved.

II.1.5 Functions of Business Process

There are three business functions that are included in this part of the process:

- 1) Help the SDM division to solve problems when business activity is keep going.
- 2) Tools for consumers to see when the production process takes place, distribution starts, and product launch will be carried out.
- 3) Provide information to employees to understand the tasks that have been assigned so that the company's goals are achieved.

II.1.6 Benefits of Business Process

After understanding the meanings, types, stages, and functions, you also need to know what are the benefits of the business process:

- 1) Know information about the situation and conditions of the company.
- 2) A guide to making long-term business projections.
- 3) Increase competitive value so that the company is able to respond to any change.
- 4) Focus on consumer needs.
- 5) Increase the efficiency and efficiency of work.
- 6) Identify opportunities and threats in order to be able to have products that fit the current of times.

II.2 Business Process Improvement (BPI)

Business Process Improvement (BPI) is a method of continuous improvement that is defined as a systematic framework designed to assist an organization in making substantial advancements in the implementation of its business processes. BPI provides a system that facilitates the streamlining of business processes by ensuring that the organization's internal and external clients receive better outputs than in the past (Harrington, 1991). Business Process Improvement or business process improvement is an activity that adds value to the transformation of input into output, be it products or services for customers, by integrating people, methods, and tools (Adinda, 2018). Tools and improvement measures can be used to facilitate business growth. The primary objective of applying the BPI Method is to find a solution to a problem in a business process; such a solution is a business process consisting of recommendations or suggestions using the supplied techniques of improvement. Improvements can be made, among other things, by modifying business processes to maximize the use of assets, minimizing the delay of a business process, fostering comprehension, and minimizing SDM or necessary production costs (Harrington, 1991).

This study only covers the third phase of the BPI, which is the Streamlining phase. Aspects of BPI:

1. Planning for Enhancement

This phase's objective is to assure success by fostering commitment. In addition, the purpose of this phase is to identify the process that will be corrected.

2. Understanding the Method

At this juncture, a comprehensive understanding of the organization's business processes is achieved. Understanding is achieved by defining business processes, developing business process models, and analysing the duration of business process activities.

3. Streamlining

In this phase, the process of streamlining will be carried out using 12 BPI- provided tools, including Bureaucracy Elimination, Duplicate Elimination, Value-Added Assessment, Simplification, Process Cycle-time Reduction, Error Proofing, and Upgrading. Simple Language, Standardization, Supplier Partnerships, Improvement of the Big Picture, Automation, and/or Machines

4. Measurements and Regulations

In this phase, the objective is to implement the already-repaired business process and to periodically monitor business processes for further enhancements.

5. Continuous improvement

In this phase, it is intended to implement periodically enhanced business processes. During this phase, the previously enhanced business process is evaluated and redefined to identify new problems that will enhance the future business process.

II.1.1 The Purpose Business Process Improvement (BPI)

The primary objective of BPI according to Harrington (1991) is to ensure that business processes:

1. Eliminate or reduce errors.
2. Minimize the waiting time (delay).
3. Use of assets.
4. Provide understanding and facilitate use.
5. Close to internal or external customers.
6. Ability to adapt to customer wishes.
7. Give companies a competitive advantage.
8. Eliminate excess spending.

II.3 Root Cause Analysis (RCA)

Root Cause Analysis is a problem-solving technique that identifies the origin, concerns, or inaccessibility of a problem. RCA requires investigators to discover solutions to a problem, comprehend the underlying causes of a situation, and accurately solve the problem, thereby preventing the recurrence of previously occurring problems. Consequently, RCA requires the identification and administration of processes, procedures, activities, behaviour, and conditions.

The following stages comprise Root Cause Analysis

a. Identify the issue. (Specify the nonconformity).

At this juncture, what must be known, defined, and described clearly is the current situation, followed by an explanation of the specific problems that are occurring.

b. Investigate the underlying cause of the issue. (investigate the underlying cause).

This is the most essential step in root cause analysis because, if the root cause of the problem is incorrectly identified, the action plan will not be able to solve the problem accurately, and the problem will likely recur. Utilize tools or methods during this phase to identify the problem's primary cause.

c. Proposing a Plan of Action (create a proposed plan of action).

At this stage, the outcomes are offered in the form of an action plan to prevent problems from reoccurring and to enhance business processes.

d. Implementing a Plan of Action (carry out the proposed action).

At this stage, the party responsible for the implementation of the action plan will be identified, as well as the means by which the action plan will be carried out. Additionally, it is crucial to establish timescales, i.e. a timetable and implementation objectives.

This phase is essential for confirming that the changes or new activities implemented have been carried out in accordance with

the action plan. Then, this stage aids in determining whether the improvement steps implemented are suitable for addressing the fundamental cause of the issue or whether they will create additional problems. Examples of activities that include monitoring and verification include internal audits of newly implemented processes, implementation of completion signs for each modified process, verifying at the beginning of the process, etc. Methods of Root Cause Analysis (RCA) include the following:

a. The Five Whys

The 5-Whys technique is the simplest way to determine the fundamental cause of a problem. This method consists of asking inquiries in order to determine the source of a problem. This strategy employs the query "Why?" Until a conclusion is reached.

Figure 2. 1 The 5-Whys (Uksw, 2016)

In general, it is recommended to ask at least five questions, but additional questions may also be required, as it is essential to continue asking questions until the true cause is identified.

II.4 Related Literature Review

Tri Susanto, Djoko Pramono, and Nanang Yudi Setiawan conducted research in 2018 with the title "Analysis and Improvement of Business Processes Using Business Process Improving Methods (BPI) (Case Study: PT. Wonojati Wijoyo)" (Susanto et al., 2018); this research improves one of the accounting and finance divisions because the business processes applied to the accountancy and finance division are still operating in an inefficient manner. Inconsistency between the calculation of wages and the wages that should be paid to employees due to frequent errors in the absence recording process, which is still performed manually by humans, is a common issue in the business process of employees. Business processes in the accounting and finance departments are frequently not completed within the specified timeframes. In addition, the Division Head of Accounting and Finance desires an assessment and enhancement of business processes. Using Five Whys Analysis and Value Chain Analysis, the researchers improved one of the accounting divisions. The Five Whys Analysis was used to identify existing problems and help the team gain a deeper understanding of the problems faced. Value Chain Analysis was used to identify the activities of the company by classifying the types of activities that support the company's goals. PT. Wonojati Wijoyo's Accounting and Finance Division's principal business processes are Accounting, Financial Reporting, and Employee Salary, as determined by business process analysis utilizing the value chain analysis and composition technique. Based on the evaluation with five whys analysis that identified the root cause of the problem with each employee's salary business process, the absence process still uses manual methods with check log paper, making it susceptible to fraud in absence recording and prone to recording errors because it is done manually by the Accounting and Finance Division staff. Based on the results of the simulation, a comparison is made between the initial business process and the recommended business process. The simulation assumes that the process takes six months to complete. On the basis of the assumption that the execution of the resulting business process advice is faster than that of the initial business process, the results of comparisons between the initial business process and business process recommendations are presented. The minimum execution time for the employee salary business process increased by 27.88%, the maximum execution time by 26.79%, and the average execution time by 27.71%.

Adeyaksa Galuh Waluyo, Ismiarta Aknuranda, and Nanang Yudi Setiawan conducted research entitled "Analysis of Business Processes on Galuh Book Stores Using the Business Process Improvement Framework" in 2018 (Galuh Waluyo et al., 2018). The bookstore operates in the retail industry. The Galuh Book Store has existed since 1998 and has continued to expand. Galuh Book Store's vision is to be the leader in the Sidoarjo book retail industry. The issue arises when the company grows, i.e., there are no written business processes that become the focus of operating the business; consequently, the decisions made can vary based on the circumstances, resulting in a less effective and efficient business process. Business Process Improvement (BPI) Framework Analysis. The first phase edited business processes using Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN), and the second phase validated the business process's process, time, and resources. Determine then the streamlining techniques used to enhance the efficacy and

effectiveness of business processes. As a consequence of the analysis, the time required for sales transactions increased by 64.37 percent, buyer transactions by 78.1 percent, price labeling by 30 percent, and goods data editing by 25.25 percent. Tri Susanto, Djoko Pramono, and Nanang Yudi Setiawan conducted research in 2018 with the title "Analysis and Improvement of Business Processes Using Business Process Improving Methods (BPI) (Case Study: PT. Wonojati Wijoyo)".

Other research Larasati (2017) conducted at the Marketing Research and Customer Service Center of PT. The Greek petrochemistry adapted the BPI method to phase 3: streamlining. The simulation's results are based on the improvement of business processes, i.e. the difference in the efficacy of the business process used to measure customer satisfaction, which is 9 days 9 hours 54 minutes and 43 seconds. The outcome of this research is a more efficient business process for making recommendations at the Marketing Research and Customer Service than the current business process.

The research uses business process improvements from weak processes that negatively impact the company's performance, so it is necessary to find the root of the problem using "five whys analysis" and process improvement using some BPI techniques and is described with Igrafx to determine the effectiveness of improvement processes by comparing old business processes and business process recommendations.

II.5 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. 2 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is the research's logical conceptualisation. Therefore, the conceptual framework is an essential step in the research process, as it frames the entire research procedure (Ukwoma & Ngulube, 2021). The conceptual framework is a logical representation of the research as a whole. Therefore, the conceptual framework is an essential step in the research process, as it provides the structure for the entire research procedure (Ukwoma & Ngulube, 2021). This study's conceptual framework is based on the authors' analysis and previous research by Ulfa & Prasetyo (2020) entitled The Study of the Financial Performance of Construction

of New College Buildings.

This research begins with the identification of a company's problems in order to obtain the business issues that are central to its discussions. The obtained business problems necessitate an analysis of business situations in order for the author to comprehend the challenges encountered by the business based on business process improvement (BPI). The study draws conclusions from the analysis of primary data sources. Interviews and observations yield primary data, while reports, books, articles, and journals provide secondary data (Sugiyono, 2017). In this investigation, companies were interviewed and observed to collect primary data. According to this data source. The authors continue to use Root Cause Analysis (RCA) to identify the source of the problem and recommend more effective and efficient business processes for companies.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

III.1 Research Design

Research methodology is a representation of the research conducted to address the problem's formula in order to realise the true purpose of the study. This chapter describes the form of research, the subject of the study, the location and time of the research, and the stages of the research.

In its research on Business Process Improvement (BPI) via Root Cause Analysis (RCA), PT. Docil Berkah Abadi employs qualitative research methods with a focus on business process problems and some case studies.

In qualitative research, nonmathematical data analysis is employed. Problems in qualitative research are regionalized in confined spaces and have low levels of variation, but the language is limitless (Burhan Bungin, 2005). In general, the objectives of qualitative research are guided by the paradigm employed by the researcher in the analysis of each case study, with the quality paradigm holding that a reality is perceived as a dual-natured fact, so that it is systematised, embodies a characteristic, conception, and contains an associative relationship, and must be understood naturally, contextually, and holistically. In its research on Business Process Improvement (BPI) via Root Cause Analysis (RCA), PT. Docil Berkah Abadi employs qualitative research methods with a focus on business process problems and some case studies.

III.2 Data Collection Method

Sources of data are anything that can provide information relevant to research. This research makes use of primary data.

According to Sugiyono (2017) primary data is the data source that supplies data to the data collector directly. Data is collected by the researchers themselves directly from the primary source or the location where the research was conducted. As primary data, researchers utilise the results of interviews conducted with research informants.

According to Joseph (2014), the success of data collection is primarily contingent on the ability of researchers to experience the social situation under study. Researchers can conduct interviews with the subject of their study and witness social situations in their natural contexts. Researchers will not end the data collection phase until they are confident that the data collected from a variety of sources and focused on the social situation being studied can answer the problem formulation from the research, so that the accuracy and credibility are not in question. Interviews are one of the techniques used to acquire data for this study's data collection method. The purpose of interviews is to obtain information from relevant informants via two-way communication. According to Joseph (2014), an interview is an interaction between an interviewer and a source of information or individual interviewed through direct communication or direct questioning about an object under study. The researcher-selected interview is a freely guided interview. According to Arikunto (2006), a freelance interview is one in which queries are asked freely while adhering to the interview's guidelines. Questions will arise throughout the interview. This interview is intended to collect pertinent information for the investigation.

III.2.1 Objects and Location of Research

The object and location of this research is the structure of the organization and the flow of PT. Docil Berkah Abadi business processes.

He is the founder and general director of Strategic Business Development. To obtain the data necessary to carry out this research, the author conducted an interview with Mr. Aldhito as the owner of PT. Docil Berkah Abadi and Mr Ghiffar Sabda as General Director of Strategic Business Development. The author also observes directly, in order to know more about the business process conducted by PT. Docil Berkah Abadi before and this interview was held so that the writer better understands the problems and conditions of

the business process that has been running in PT. Berkah Abadi.

III. 2.3 Time and Location of The Investigation

The investigation was conducted at PT. Docil Berkah Abadi at Komplek Ruko, Jl. Kopo Mas No.18A, Margasuka, Kec. Babakan Ciparay, Kabupaten Bandung, Jawa Barat 40227 The investigation was conducted over a period of five months, beginning in January 2023 and ending in June 2023.

III.3 Data Analysis Method

To analysis qualitative data, the authors will use a thematic analysis approach. Thematic analysis is one of the methods used in analysis data aimed at finding patterns or themes. Based on data collected by the researchers. This strategis one of the most effective methods for research that requires in-depth and detailed analysis of existing data. In fact, this analysis is considered a core skill or basic knowledge to perform analysis in qualitative research (Yadav, 2022). This type of analysis is the most suitable type to be used by authors to analysis quality data. Thisis due to the type of interview used by the author, that is, his interview tends to give answers that will form a theme or pattern, so by using thematic analysis the author will categorize the respondents' answers based on the same theme.

III.3.1 Research Phase

Figure 3. 1 Research Phase

1. Literature Studies

The purpose of literature study activities is to acquire data that will serve as the foundation for the discussion of the theory preparation used in research. The sources utilized as libraries are scholarly journals and previous scientific works.

2. Data collection

PT. Docil Berkah Abadi the interview technique for data collection. The goal of PT. Docil Berkah Abadi is to understand the workflow and business processes used, as well as the impediments encountered through daily activities until data processing in PT. Docil Berkah Abadi via tasks within each organizational structure employed

3. Identification of early business processes

Identify initial business processes using workflow explanation tables. In order to identify the initial business process, it is necessary to describe in depth the problems and business processes utilized by each division or organizational structure within PT. Docil Berkah Abadi.

4. Business Process Modelling

Business Process Notation with Business Process Modelling using the basis of custom flowchart techniques to create a

graphical model of the operations of business processes. A business process model is a network of graphic objects consisting of activities and flow rules that define the sequence of events Root Cause Analysis.

5. Applying Root Cause Analysis (RCA)

The Root Cause Analysis (RCA) is based on the following steps:

- 1) Defining the issue (defining the lack of confidence);
- 2) Investigate the underlying cause of the issue;

In this investigation, the following phases of root cause analysis (RCA) application will be implemented:

- 1) The phase specifies the issue

The data analysis is based on the outcomes of described business processes from the previous stage of research. Then, a summary of frequently occurring problems or business processes whose course is repeated from one division to another is compiled based on the data analysis of problems that have been identified. Also designed business processes that do not align with PT. Docil Berkah Abadi objectives.

- 2) Determine the primary cause of the issue.

In this phase, the instruments and methods utilized are derived from the method. RCA is a 5-Whys interview technique that focuses on the question "Why a problem occurs?" To investigate the problem's root cause until conclusions can be drawn. In this study, the interview data are the primary data that will be analyzed to solve the research problem. Following the interview, data is summarized and then input into units to be categorized based on the business process. The results of interview data collection and processing were then summarized using the 5-Whys technique.

- 3) Proposing a Plan of Action

Submit an action plan based on the results of the enhanced business processes resulting from the implementation of streamlining techniques.

- 4) Improve business processes using BPI and streamlining strategies

Improve business processes with improved outcomes and describe the application of technology to the enhancement of business process outcomes and process improvement through streamlining techniques. Comparison of business process effectiveness and effectiveness levels Streamlining focuses on enhancing business process efficiency, effectiveness, and adaptability. According to the needs of business process improvement, there are 12 tools available, including bureaucracy, elimination, duplication elimination, value-added assessment, simplification, process reduction, error proofing, upgrading, simple language, standardization, supplier partnerships, big picture improvement, and automation (Harrington, 1991).

6. Implementation new Business Process Improvement

Implementation of a business process is visualized using a flowchart of business processes accompanied by a timeline and a list of those responsible.

7. Identification of Business Improvement Processes

Identification of business improvement processes identifies new processes that need to be defined in greater detail and analysis the application of technology to the enhancement of business processes.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

IV.1 Analysis

Business situation analysis is aimed at gathering and analyzing the internal and external factors that influence a business so that the current state can be identified and able to make informed decisions. This study uses PESTLE model to analyzing PT. Docil Berkah Abadi external situation, and using SWOT based on the primary data to analyze its internal situation.

Table 4. 1 Internal Analysis with SWOT

INTERNAL	
	Factors affected within my industry
STRENGTH	When you consider that this business is a family business, work coordination amongst the staff is really good. Most of the employees are still related to their families.
	The cost of document generating services is not excessively high, but the output's performance and quality are excellent.
WEAKNESS	Diversion of labor responsibilities and authority might result from an unsatisfactory organizational structure.
	Due to the company's modest size and lack of staff, it can become somewhat overburdened when the amount of work increases.
OPPORTUNITY	Companies become more efficient at accomplishing tasks and work as office technology and the number of personnel employed expand.
THREAT	Because of the family principle, there is no professional competition among employees.

Table 4. 2 External Analysis with PESTLE

EXTERNAL			
	External factors to consider	Factors affected within my industry	Importance to organisation
POLITICAL	Government policy Political stability Tax Industry regulations Global trade agreements and or restrictions	A government that changes taxes too much makes it difficult for PT. Docil Berkah Abadi to adjust the sale price, because it has a small margin.	This leads the producer to have to be able to adjust the COGS to the sale price due to high taxes.
ECONOMIC	Exchange rates Globalisation Economic growth/ decline Inflation Interest rates Cost of living Labour costs Consumer spending habits	Raw material fluctuations have an impact on the selling price and profit made.	affecting the COGS optimization approach and the sustainability level of the business
SOCIAL	Consumer trends/ tastes, Fashions Consumer buying habits Lifestyle factors Career attitudes Work-life balance Population demographics	Since the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi is young, the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi must be able to adjust to the increasingly fluctuating demand of the market.	The RND must be able to adapt to increasingly creative market demands.

TECHNOLOGY	Automation technologies Innovation Disruptive technologies Social networking Upgrades Robotics Artificial Intelligence Security	Lack of creativity as a result of the workforce's inability to adapt to the modern age	Because of the strong family traditions, it can be challenging to comprehend the value of technology in maximizing labor.
LEGAL	Employment law labour law Health and safety regulations Common law Local safety	Having weaker legal protections for employee health and safety	In this company, the value of employee health and safety is not given enough consideration.
ENVIRONMENTAL	Environmental restrictions imposed by in-country governments Sustainable resources CSR (Corporate social responsibility) Ethical sourcing Transportation Procurement Supply chain management Future pandemics	Due to the fact that family businesses are not as concerned with maintaining the environment's welfare or the consequences of existing garbage.	Due to the dearth of fresh ideas from young and compatible new employees, the corporation is more concerned with the company than the environment.

Five Whys is used to find the root problem of an evaluated business process. With Root Cause Analysis (RCA) can see that there are problems in the business process from stock in to stock out that hinder the development of PT. Docil Berkah Abadi due to too long business processes as well as hindering the cash flow of the company, Five Whys is described as follows:

Figure 4. 1 Five Whys PT. Docil Berkah Abadi

After an interview with the 5 Whys author, it can be concluded that the occurrence of errors because of the beginning of the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi formed originated from the hobby of the founder in the automotive sector and looked at the opportunities of demand in the auto accessories. This business process has traditional methods because it's not too much to look at PT. Docil Berkah

Abadi towards professional. With the significant increase in sales, the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi party is not ready to face the development of business with competitors who are already more systematic in the business process. Then the problem – the problem began to emerge and could not be solved as the course of sales increased every period. Technically running problems in the field are side-by-side with unhealthy cash flow due to the amount of demand increasing every time.

Phase 1 (Organizing for Improvement) includes the introduction of the organization to obtain information related to the organization and business processes in the organization for later improvements to the critical business process obtained. Identification includes a description of the organizational environment, history, organizational structure, as well as business processes present on PT. Docil Berkah Abadi.

Phase 2 (Understanding the Process) in this study includes the creation of a graphic notation of the current (existing) business processes on PT. Docil Berkah Abadi in the form of SOP (Standard Operational Procedures) to give a structured explanation in modelling the business process loaded in the flowchart. The creation of graphic notation on this research is carried out against the entire business process that exists from the process of stock in to stock out. The results of the interview can be explained through flowchart with the following symbol rules:

Table 4. 3 Symbol Flowchart

	Start/End indicates the completion or completion of the process.
	Processing, indicating that the activity or work is being implemented.
	Represents the physical documents used in one process.
	Database, representing the document in the input into the system.
	Decision, a symbol that indicates confirmation. Process flow to the right if the decision is “no” and to down the decision is “Yes”.

After the interview, the author can describe the initial business process through the flowchart as follows:

Figure 4. 3 Flowchart Early Process Business part 1

Figure 4. 4 Flowchart Early Process Business part 2

Figure 4. 5 Flowchart Early Process Business part 3

According to the results of data collection and interviews, there are 8 divisions, namely admin seller, admin public, admin scan, finance, packer, supplier, warehouse (stock in) and stock out (stock out) to run business processes for current conditions (existing) on the business process from stock in to stock out. SOP on the running business processes there are 65 processes loaded in job description as follows:

- **Admin Seller:**

1. Export list of goods sold from all platforms
2. Export list of sold items to Database
3. Print Receipt and send list receipt to admin scan
4. List of goods sold to public admin
5. Excel automatically creates a list of sold items

- **Admin Public:**

1. Receive a list of sold items from Admin Seller
2. Send list of goods sold to the warehouse
3. Export List Returns Goods from All Platforms
4. Return of goods to warehouse.
5. Receive list non-damaged returns to increase inventory fromwarehouse
6. Receive list returning damaged items to increase waste fromwarehouse and send to finance
7. Receive a list of items that are not suitable for purchase ordersfrom the warehouse
8. Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Coming Goods
9. Make a Purchase Order according to inventory needs
10. Send a Purchase Order to Finance
11. Acceptance of Purchase Order
12. Send a Purchase Order to the Supplier
13. Send a list Purchase Order to the Warehouse
14. Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Coming Goods
15. Receive all reports from Admin Scan
16. Sending Packer Reports to Finance
17. Provide proof of payment to the supplier

- **Admin Scan:**

1. Scan Sold Goods with Receipt
2. Receive goods was packed by Team Packer
3. Scan items and packer team
4. Send all reports to admin public
5. Send Packer List and Items in Packing for Calculate Salary tofinance

- **Finance:**

1. Receive Packer Reports to Estimate Packer Salary
2. Receive list returning damaged items to increase waste
3. Receiving a Purchase Order
4. Payment order to the Supplier
5. Sending Proof of Payment to Public Admin

- **Packer:**

1. Receive selling goods from the warehouse
2. Packing sold items
3. Scan Selling goods to Admin Scan
4. Send selling goods to the warehouse

- **Supplier:**

1. Receive Purchase Orders from Public Admin
2. Receive proof of purchase order payment from admin public
3. Send order to the warehouse
4. Receive Adjustments of Delivered Goods and Purchase Orders from admin public

- **Warehouse (Stock In):**

1. Receiving a Purchase Order from admin public
2. Goods to Warehouse from supplier
3. Put barcodes for all types of items
4. Scan every barcode
5. Barcode in Excel
6. Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Goods already in barcode scan
7. Write a letter of incoming goods and purchase order
8. Sending letters and Qty items that are inappropriate to admin public
9. Goods into the warehouse
10. Goods added Inventory
11. Receiving a return letter
12. Sort of goods
13. Reports of damaged items send to admin public
14. Scan of Damaged Returned Goods
15. Scan of returned items that are not damaged
16. Returning damaged goods into waste
17. Returned items not damaged enter the inventory

- **Warehouse (Stock Out):**

1. Receive list selling goods from the admin public
2. Prepare the sold items
3. Scan goods for sale
4. Delivering Goods to Packer
5. Receive packaged items from Team Packer
6. Scan with outgoing items. (Double Check)
7. Return the sold goods to the warehouse
8. Send selling goods to the expedition

The authors conclude that the business process that is already running PT. Docil Berkah Abadi is ineffective and takes a lot of time for each process. This is an obstacle for PT. Docil Berkah Abadi to grow, because the business process that has been running so far is ineffective. It also affects fixed cost and variable cost.

PT. Docil Berkah Abadi has serious problems in its business process because the previously running business processes are not effective and result in too large fixed costs incurred by PT. Docil berkah Abadi This is the time from the beginning of the order acceptance until the goods are sold too long. The number of employees who have been discharged does not correspond to the salary costs already incurred by PT. Docil Berkah Abadi this is a very expensive rental because you have to store a lot of stock. The amount of funds to be issued by the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi is not equal to the amount of money obtained by PT. Docil Berkah Abadi from various sales platforms. The business process through the stocking of goods is no longer effective. This causes fixed cost and variable cost that are too swollen making PT. Docil Berkah Abadi cannot optimize the existing cash flow. From some of these problems, it can be concluded that PT. Docil Berkah Abadi cannot optimize business processes and cause delayed decision-making due to ineffective cash flow as well as hindering the problems and development of PT. Docil Berkah Abadi.

IV.2 Business Solution

PT. Docil Berkah Abadi has the hope of reducing human error due to the too long business process, placing the goods into an important thing to pay attention to PT. Docil Berkah Abadi, because it will hinder the cash flow. Fix cost and variable cost that will also affect the inhibition of PT. Docil Berkah Abadi to grow. The process of melting funds from various platforms has become a problem for the process of stocking goods that are not small. Renting expensive buildings for warehouses becomes a burden that reduces the budget for marketing. Some of these things are hopes PT. Docil Berkah Abadi which is a serious problem and it is the task of PT. Docil Berkah Abadi to solve the problem.

Phase 3 Improvement of business processes is a stage that aims to produce a business process improvement plan based on the root problem of the current business process. Improving business processes is done using the tools of Business Process Improvement. The results of the business process improvement plan, will be used to draw up business process recommendations.

Table 4. 4 Business Process Improvement Plan

Division	Early Business Process	Streamlining	Recommendation Business Process
Admin Seller	List of goods sold to public admin	Upgrading	List of goods sold and receipt
	Excel automatically creates a list of sold items	Upgrading	Send list of goods sold and receipt to admin public
	<i>Early Business Process</i>	Streamlining	Recommendation Business Process
	<i>Receive a list of sold items from Admin Seller</i>	Upgrading	Admin Public receive and confirm list of goods sold and receipt
	<i>Send list of goods sold to the warehouse</i>	Upgrading	Send list of goods sold and receipt to supplier
	<i>Export List Returns Goods from All Platforms</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
	<i>Return of goods to warehouse</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
	<i>Receive list non-damaged returns to increase inventory from warehouse</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
	<i>Receive list returning damaged items to increase waste from warehouse and send to finance</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
	<i>Receive a list of items that are not suitable for purchase orders from the warehouse</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate

<i>Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Coming Goods</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Make a Purchase Order according to inventory needs</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Send a Purchase Order to Finance</i>	Upgrading	Send list of goods sold to finance
<i>Acceptance of Purchase Order</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Send a Purchase Order to the Supplier</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Send a list Purchase Order to the Warehouse</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Coming Goods</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Early Business Process</i>	Streamlining	Recommendation Business Process
<i>Receive all reports from Admin Scan</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Sending Packer Reports to Finance</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Provide proof of payment to the supplier</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Scan Sold Goods with Receipt</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Receive goods was packed by Team Packer</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate

<i>Scan items and packer team</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Send all reports to admin public</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Send Packer List and Items in Packing for Calculate Salary to finance</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Receive Packer Reports to Estimate Packer Salary</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Receive list returning damaged items to increase waste</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Receiving a Purchase Order</i>	Upgrading	Finance receive and confirm list of goods sold
<i>Payment order to the Supplier</i>	Upgrading	Finance send payment to supplier
<i>Sending Proof of Payment to Public Admin</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Receive selling goods from the warehouse</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Packing sold items</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Scan Selling goods to Admin Scan</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Send selling goods to the warehouse</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Receive Purchase Orders from Public Admin</i>	Upgrading	Supplier receive list of goods sold and receipt

<i>Early Business Process</i>	Streamlining	Recommendation Business Process
<i>Receive proof of purchase order payment from admin public</i>	Upgrading	Supplier receive payment from finance
<i>Send order to the warehouse</i>	Upgrading	Supplier prepare and packing goods sold
<i>Receive Adjustments of Delivered Goods and Purchase Orders from admin public</i>	Upgrading	Supplier send goods sold to expedition
<i>Receiving a Purchase Order from admin public</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Goods to Warehouse from supplier</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Put barcodes for all types of items</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Scan every barcode</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Barcode in Excel</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Goods already in barcode scan</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Write a letter of incoming goods and purchase order</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Sending letters and Qty items that are inappropriate to admin public</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Goods into the warehouse</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate

<i>Goods added Inventory</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Receiving a return letter</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Sort of goods</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Reports of damaged items send to admin public</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Scan of Damaged Returned Goods</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Early Business Process</i>	Streamlining	Recommendation Business Process
<i>Scan of returned items that are not damaged</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Returning damaged goods into waste</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Returned items not damaged enter the inventory</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Receive list selling goods from the admin public</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Prepare the sold items</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Scan goods for sale</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Delivering Goods to Packer</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate

<i>Receive packaged items from Team Packer</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Scan with outgoing items. (Double Check)</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Return the sold goods to the warehouse</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate
<i>Send selling goods to the expedition</i>	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate

From 65 (sixty-five) business processes from stock in to stock out in eliminate to 12 (twelve) there are 52 (fifty-two) business procedures that are in bureaucracy elimination, among others:

• **Admin Public :**

1. Export List Returns Goods from All Platforms
2. Return of goods to warehouse
3. Receive list non-damaged returns to increase inventory from warehouse
4. Receive list returning damaged items to increase waste from warehouse and send to finance
5. Receive a list of items that are not suitable for purchase orders from the warehouse
6. Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Coming Goods
7. Make a Purchase Order according to inventory needs
8. Send a Purchase Order to Finance
9. Acceptance of Purchase Order
10. Send a Purchase Order to the Supplier
11. Send a list Purchase Order to the Warehouse
12. Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Coming Goods
13. Receive all reports from Admin Scan
14. Sending Packer Reports to Finance
15. Provide proof of payment to the supplier

There are 15 business processes that are eliminated because the business process is too long in the public administration making the performance of the public admin not go well. Public admin who tends to have direct contact with several other divisions causes too much miss communication so that, data with actual often occurs discrepancies. By shortening the public admin process can adjust data to actual more optimally because of the coordination that is run less.

• **Admin Scan**

1. Scan Sold Goods with Receipt
2. Receive goods was packed by Team Packer
3. Scan items and packer team
4. Send all reports to admin public
5. Send Packer List and Items in Packing for Calculate Salary to finance

Business processes on the admin division are immediately scan in eliminate, which will reduce staff and staff burden.

• **Finance**

1. Receive Packer Reports to Estimate Packer Salary
2. Receiving a Purchase Order
3. Sending Proof of Payment to Public Admin

In the finance division there are 3 (three) business processes that are eliminated because the finance side has barriers in regulating cash flow, this is due to too many human errors in the other division, in this division the finance party can alleviate fixed cost and variable cost of Rp 350,000.00,00,- (three hundred fifty million rupiah) each month with the ratio of fixed costs and variable cost compared to the existing income of 42% (forty-two percent) in the previous business process to 17% (seventeen percent) down by 25% (twenty-five percent).

- **Packer**

1. Receive selling goods from the warehouse
2. Packing sold items
3. Scan Selling goods to Admin Scan
4. Send selling goods to the warehouse

At the packer division all business processes are in the eliminate and reduction of the division, due to too many human errors and felt ineffective. By improving the business process, you can reduce the payroll of the packer division.

- **Warehouse (Stock In)**

1. Receiving a Purchase Order from admin public
2. Goods to Warehouse from supplier
3. Put barcodes for all types of items
4. Scan every barcode
5. Barcode in Excel
6. Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Goods already in barcode scan
7. Write a letter of incoming goods and purchase order
8. Sending letters and Qty items that are inappropriate to admin public
9. Goods into the warehouse
10. Goods added Inventory
11. Receiving a return letter
12. Sort of goods
13. Reports of damaged items send to admin public
14. Scan of Damaged Returned Goods
15. Scan of returned items that are not damaged
16. Returning damaged goods into waste
17. Returned items not damaged enter the inventory

- **Warehouse (Stock Out)**

1. Receive list selling goods from the admin public
2. Prepare the sold items
3. Scan goods for sale
4. Delivering Goods to Packer
5. Receive packaged items from Team Packer
6. Scan with outgoing items. (Double Check)
7. Return the sold goods to the warehouse
8. Send selling goods to the expedition

In the warehouse division the author proposed to reduce the warehousing division because there are too many business processes that are considered ineffective and the costs spent on the rental of buildings for warehouses as well as the stocking that is swollen, making the expenditure in the Warehouse division huge.

It can be concluded that bureaucracy elimination has the following benefits:

1. Reduce process time.
2. Reduce the costs
3. Reduce the cycle time (cycle time)
4. Increase employee morals, because they are involved in higher decisions
5. Increase employee confidence by being involved responsibly.

There are also business processes that the author suggests for upgrading which are:

• **Admin Seller**

1. List of goods sold to public admin to list of goods sold and receipt
2. Excel automatically creates a list of sold items to send list of goods sold and receipt to admin public

• **Admin Public**

1. Receive a list of sold items from Admin Seller to admin Public receive and confirm list of goods sold and receipt
2. Send list of goods sold to the warehouse to send list of goods sold and receipt to supplier

• **Finance**

1. Receiving a Purchase Order to finance receive and confirm list of goods sold
2. Payment order to the Supplier to finance send payment to supplier

• **Supplier**

1. Receive Purchase Orders from Public Admin to Supplier receive list of goods sold and receipt
2. Receive proof of purchase order payment from admin public to supplier receive payment from finance
3. Send order to the warehouse to supplier prepare and packing goods sold
4. Receive Adjustments of Delivered Goods and Purchase Orders from admin public to supplier send goods sold to expedition

Upgrading here is intended to adjust the business process because it has already done eliminate on the previous business process, it requires adjustment between divisions because the earlier business process is very different from the proposal business process.

After the business process improvement (BPI), the author proposes a new business process and is described in the flowchart as follows:

Table 4. 5 Flowchart Recommendation Business Process PT. Docil Berkah Abadi

From the flow chart above the author can conclude that the business process can be simplified to complete the process from stock in to stock out. After some of the above processes, the author can simplify the job description and the previous field position to several field positions to complete the stock in to stock out process, as follows:

- **Admin Seller:**
 1. Export list of goods sold from all platforms
 2. List of goods sold and receipt
 3. Send list of goods sold and receipt to admin public
- **Admin Public:**
 1. Admin Public receive and confirm list of goods sold and receipt
 2. Send list of goods sold and receipt to supplier
 3. Send list of goods sold to finance
- **Finance:**
 1. Finance receive and confirm list of goods sold
 2. Finance send payment to supplier
- **Supplier:**
 1. Supplier receive list of goods sold and receipt
 2. Supplier receive payment from finance
 3. Supplier prepare and packing goods sold
 4. Supplier send goods sold to expedition

IV.3 Implementation Plan & Justification

After making improvements using Business Process Improvement (BPI) through Root Cause Analysis (RCA), the authors recommended a new business process. From the outcome of the presentation of new business processes against the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi party, the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi party agrees to use new business because it is more effective for each process. After the next interview using the new business process, the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi party can reduce fixed cost and variable cost by Rp350.000.000,00.- (three hundred and fifty million) each month. By reducing the number of business processes that initially passed 65 (sixty-five) processes to 12 (twelve), this fixed the business problems that previously became faster. Because the new business process is simpler, it is easier for the financial parties to calculate cash flow and to organize funds for the development of the company. Marketers are more creative in formulating sales strategies because of the larger funding budgets than before. And after improving the business process, the writer can shorten the time of business process every day from 977 (Nine hundred and seventy-seven) minutes to 148 (one hundred-fourty-eight) minutes.

Table 4. 6 Time Table Early Business Process and New Business Process

Division	Early Business Process	Time Table (Minute) Early Business Process	Time Table	New Business Process	Time Table (Minute) New Business Process
Admin Seller	Export list of goods sold from all platforms	15	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
	Import list of sold items to Database	5	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0

<i>Early Business Process</i>	Time (Minute) Early Business Process	Table Early	Time Table	New Business Process	Time (Minute) New Business Process	Table New
<i>Print Receipt and send list receipt to admin scan</i>	15		Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0	
<i>List of goods sold to public admin</i>	1		Upgrading	List of goods sold and receipt	15	
<i>Excel automatically creates a list of sold items</i>	1		Upgrading	Send list of goods sold and receipt to admin public	1	
<i>Receive a list of sold items from Admin Seller</i>	1		Upgrading	Admin Public receive and confirm list of goods sold and receipt	15	
<i>Send list of goods sold to the warehouse</i>	1		Upgrading	Send list of goods sold and receipt to supplier	1	
<i>Export List Returns Goods from All Platforms</i>	15		Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0	
<i>Return of goods to warehouse.</i>	30		Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0	
<i>Receive list non- damaged returns to increase inventory from warehouse</i>	1		Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0	
<i>Receive list returning damaged items to increase waste from warehouse and send to finance</i>	1		Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0	
<i>Receive a list of items that are not suitable for purchase orders from the warehouse</i>	1		Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0	
<i>Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Coming Goods</i>	15		Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0	
<i>Early Business Process</i>	Time (Minute) Early Business Process	Table Early	Time Table	New Business Process	Time (Minute) New Business Process	Table New
<i>Make a Purchase Order according to inventory needs</i>	15		Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0	
<i>Send a Purchase Order to Finance</i>	1		Upgrading	Send list of goods sold to finance	1	

<i>Acceptance of Purchase Order</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Send a Purchase Order to the Supplier</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Send a list Purchase Order to the Warehouse</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Coming Goods</i>	15	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Receive all reports from Admin Scan</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Sending Packer Reports to Finance</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Provide proof of payment to the supplier</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Scan Sold Goods with Receipt</i>	60	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Receive goods was packed by Team Packer</i>	15	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Scan items and packer team</i>	15	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Send all reports to admin public</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Send Packer List and Items in Packing for Calculate Salary to finance</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Early Business Process</i>	Time Table (Minute) Early Business Process	Time Table	New Business Process	Time Table (Minute) New Business Process
<i>Receive Packer Reports to Estimate Packer Salary</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Receive list returning damaged items to increase waste</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Receiving a Purchase Order</i>	1	Upgrading	Finance receive and confirm list of goods sold	15
<i>Payment order to the Supplier</i>	5	Upgrading	Finance send payment to supplier	15
<i>Sending Proof of Payment to Public Admin</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0

<i>Receive selling goods from the warehouse</i>	15	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Packing sold items</i>	120	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Scan Selling goods to Admin Scan</i>	15	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Send selling goods to the warehouse</i>	60	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Receive Purchase Orders from Public Admin</i>	1	Upgrading	Supplier receive list of goods sold and receipt	5
<i>Receive proof of purchase order payment from admin public</i>	1	Upgrading	Supplier receive payment from finance	5
<i>Send order to the warehouse</i>	120	Upgrading	Supplier prepare and packing goods sold	60
<i>Receive Adjustments of Delivered Goods and Purchase Orders from admin public</i>	5	Upgrading	Supplier send goods sold to expedition	15
<i>Early Business Process</i>	Time Table (Minute) Early Business Process	Time Table	New Business Process	Time Table (Minute) New Business Process
<i>Receiving a Purchase Order from admin public</i>	5	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Goods to Warehouse from supplier</i>	30	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Put barcodes for all types of items</i>	60	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Scan every barcode</i>	15	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Barcode in Excel</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Adjusting the Purchase Order with the Goods already in barcode scan</i>	15	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Write a letter of incoming goods and purchase order</i>	5	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Sending letters and Qty items that are inappropriate to admin public</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0

<i>Goods into the warehouse</i>	30	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Goods added Inventory</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Receiving a return letter</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Sort of goods</i>	60	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Reports of damaged items send to admin public</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Scan of Damaged Returned Goods</i>	15	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Scan of returned items that are not damaged</i>	15	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Early Business Process</i>	Time Table (Minute) Early Business Process	Time Table	New Business Process	Time Table (Minute) New Business Process
<i>Returning damaged goods into waste</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Returned items not damaged enter the inventory</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Receive list selling goods from the admin public</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Prepare the sold items</i>	60	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Scan goods for sale</i>	15	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Delivering Goods to Packer</i>	30	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Receive packaged items from Team Packer</i>	5	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Scan with outgoing items. (Double Check)</i>	30	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Return the sold goods to the warehouse</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0
<i>Send selling goods to the expedition</i>	1	Bureaucracy Elimination	Eliminate	0

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

V.1 Conclusion

Based on the research conducted on PT. Docil Berkah Abadi, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Based on the evaluation with five whys analysis obtained the root problem on each business process from starting stock in and stock out that is basically the business process running before has a long process and too many divisions involved, causing the occurrence of human error that prevents the finance division to optimize the cash flow.
2. Based on the improvement with business process improvement (BPI), business processes that previously had 65 (sixty-five) processes can be shortened to 12 (twelve), ranging from stock in to stock out. With this, the finance party can reduce the fixed cost and variable cost of Rp350.000.000.00.- (three hundred fifty million rupiah) each month and optimize the existing cash flow for the future business development budget through the marketing division.
3. Based on the analysis and improvement of the authors, the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi party strongly agrees with the proposal business process. Because it can relieve the burden of all divisions despite the proximity between the divisions, because of the negotiation process and good policy all parties accept proposals to the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi goal. And after improving the business process, the writer can shorten the time of business process every day from 977 (Nine hundred and seventy-seven) minutes to 148 (one hundred-fourty-eight) minutes.

V.2 Recommendation

Based on the analysis process carried out on PT. Docil Berkah Abadi, the authors recommend that the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi party can better optimize the course of business processes to improve the financial performance significantly by comparing it with its competitors. Since there are still many obstacles that will occur even though there are already improvements in the proposal of new business processes, given the rapid development of technology that is not overdue, the PT. Docil Berkah Abadi party must be more innovative in creative marketing to compete with its competitors.

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REFERENCES

1. ADINDA, R. N. (2018). *PENGARUH PERTUMBUHAN PERUSAHAAN, UMUR PERUSAHAAN, PERGANTIAN AUDITOR, DAN STRUKTUR MODAL TERHADAP KETEPATAN WAKTU PENYAMPAIAN LAPORAN KEUANGAN*.
2. Arikunto, S. (2006). *Prosedur Penelitian: suatu pendekatan praktek*.
3. Burhan Bungin, M. , H. (2005). *Metodologi penelitian kuantitatif: komunikasi, ekonomi dan kebijakan publik serta ilmu-ilmu sosial lainnya* (2nd ed.). Depok : Prenadamedia Group.
4. Galuh Waluyo, A., Aknuranda, I., & Yudi Setiawan, N. (2018). Analisis Proses Bisnis Pada Toko Buku Galuh Menggunakan Business Process Improvement Framework. In *Jurnal Pengembangan Teknologi Informasi dan Ilmu Komputer* (Vol. 2, Issue 12). <http://j-ptiik.ub.ac.id>
5. Harrington, H. J. (1991). *Improving business processes* (1st ed., Vol. 3). MCB UP Ltd.

6. H. James Harrington, E. K. C. Esseling, & H. van Nimwegen. (1997). (*Harrington, 1999*). *Business Process Improvement begins with the mapping of the current business process*. (Illustrated). McGraw Hill Professional.
7. J. Mike Jacka, & Paulette J. Keller. (2009). *Business_Process_Mapping_Workbook*. JohnWiley & Sons.
8. Joseph, T. (2014). Mediating War and Peace: Mass Media and International Conflict. *India Quarterly*, 70(3), 225–240. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0974928414535292>
9. Laguna, M., & Marklund, J. (2018). *Business Process Modeling, Simulation and Design*. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315162119>
10. Larasati, S. D., Wicaksono, S. A., & Wardani, N. H. (2017). *Perbaikan Proses Bisnis Menggunakan Metode Business Process Improvement (BPI) (Studi Pada Bagian Riset Pemasaran dan Pusat Pelayanan Pelanggan PT. Petrokimia Gresik)* (Vol. 1, Issue 11). <http://j-ptiik.ub.ac.id>
11. Mathias Weske. (2007). *Business Process Management: Concepts, Languages, Architectures: Vol. illustrated*. Springer Science & Business Media.
12. Mathias Weske. (2012). *Business Process Management Concepts, Languages, Architectures* (2nd ed.). Springer.
13. Putri, N. L., Wedayanti, A., Kadek, N., Wirdiani, A., Ketut, I., & Purnawan, A. (n.d.). *Evaluasi Aspek Usability pada Aplikasi Simalu Menggunakan Metode Usability Testing*. 7(2).
14. Setiyadi, A., & Budi Setiawan, E. (2017). Sistem Informasi Pengumuman Program Studi Di Perguruan Tinggi X. *Lontar Komputer : Jurnal Ilmiah Teknologi Informasi*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.24843/lkjiti.2017.v08.i01.p02>
15. Sugiyono. (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif*.
16. Susanto, T., Pramono, D., & Setiawan, N. Y. (2018). *Analisis Dan Perbaikan Proses Bisnis Menggunakan Metode Business Process Improvement (BPI) (Studi Kasus: PT. Wonojati Wijoyo)* (Vol. 2, Issue 12). <http://j-ptiik.ub.ac.id>
17. Uksw, S. (2016). The Application of Fishbone Diagram Analisis to Improve School Quality.
18. *DINAMIKA ILMU*, 16, 59. <https://doi.org/10.21093/di.v16i1.262>
19. Ukwoma, S. C., & Ngulube, P. (2021). Research Productivity and the Citation of Open and Distance Learning Journals (2009-2018): A Citation Analysis. *American Journal of Distance Education*, 36, 193–207.
20. Ulfa, Z. M., & Prasetyo, A. D. (2020). Financial Feasibility Study of the Construction of New High School Building (Case Study of XYZ Foundation). *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5(4). <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejbmr.2020.5.4.467>
21. Yadav, D. (2022). Criteria for Good Qualitative Research: A Comprehensive Review. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 31(6), 679–689. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-021-00619-0>

APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1.1 : Warehouse Photos

APPENDIX 1. 2 : Offline Interview Photos

APPENDIX 1.3 : Offline Interview Answer

- Bagaimana terbentuk PT. Docil Berkah Abadi?

PT. Docil Berkah Abadi: Awal mula terbentuknya bisnis adalah berdasarkan hobi saya pribadi sebagai founder yaitu dalam otomotif, awalnya saya melihat peluang dari teman-teman dan club motor saya, lalu saya mencoba untuk membuat sampel aksesoris otomotif, ternyata demand semakin tinggi, oleh karena saya coba kembangkan pelan-pelan. Pada akhirnya alhamdulillah dari iseng-iseng ternyata bisnis ini mulai berkembang pesat setelah saya coba jual di marketplace.

- Apa tujuan dari PT. Docil Berkah Abadi?

PT. Docil Berkah Abadi: Tujuan awalnya emang untuk motor saya pribadi, namunkarena dari mulut ke mulut akhirnya produk yang saya buat 1 pcs jadi beberapa pcs untuk club motor saya. Jadi kalo ditanya mengenai tujuan ya saya juga asalnya hobidan jadi bisnis. Jadi tujuannya hanya untuk memperluas lapangan pekerjaan saja untuk beberapa orang yang membutuhkan, dan mudah-mudahan menjadi bisnis yang lebih professional.

- Bagaimana bisnis proses yang sudah dijalani?

PT. Docil Berkah Abadi: Sampai sekarang bisnis saya masih berjalan dengan cara tradisional melalui 65 proses yang terbilang panjang, karena pada awalnya juga masih memakai cara tradisional mengikuti demand yang ada.

- Apa kendala dari proses bisnis yang sudah dijalani?

PT. Docil Berkah Abadi: Karena permintaan yang meningkat secara signifikan saya sudah mengalami beberapa kendala seperti lambatnya proses, salah kordinasi, mengendapnya stock yang terlalu lama, perhitungan cash flow yang tidak optimal, besarnya fix cost dan variable cost, susah nya berkembang bisnis karena permintaanyang tinggi dengan kondisi perusahaan yang belum siap.

- Apa yang pihak PT harapkan dengan memperbaiki bisnis proses?

PT. Docil Berkah Abadi: Harapan saya semoga dengan adanya Primaderi disini dapat membantu saya untuk memperbaiki bisnis proses yang ada, dan menimalisir kendala yang saya tadi sebutkan, agar saya dapat mempercepat proses tumbuhnya bisnis saya.